

1 **40 years of sharing economy research: An intellectual and**
2 **cognitive structures analysis**

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17
18 **Abstract**

19 This study aims to analyze the intellectual and cognitive structures of the sharing economy as
20 a field of research. Adopting an integrated bibliometric approach of citation, co-citation, and
21 co-word analysis, this study analyzes 941 articles published on Web of Science from 1978 to
22 2019. Findings reveal that despite there being a latent concentration in citations distribution,
23 the ascending and descending influence patterns discovered over time indicate a dynamic flow
24 and healthy growth of the field. The analysis of the intellectual structure identifies four main
25 areas of research, with hospitality and tourism being the most developed, and the journals about
26 hospitality being the preferred channel for research into the sharing economy. Finally, for the
27 cognitive structure analysis, in-depth strategic diagrams, thematic evolution, and trend analysis
28 disclose some research gaps. Thus, we contribute to the sharing economy literature by
29 inductively synthesizing, and organizing SE research, and by proposing future research
30 directions.

31 **Keywords:** Sharing economy; Intellectual structure; Cognitive structure; Citation analysis; Co-
32 citation analysis; Co-occurrence analysis

33 **1. Introduction**

34 Even though sharing may be not a new practice, the sharing economy (SE) is a recent
35 phenomenon (Eckhardt et al., 2019; Hossain, 2020), boosted by the Internet and digital
36 platforms (Belk, 2014; Sutherland and Jarrahi, 2018), that has received increased attention from
37 academics, industry associations, practitioners, governments and individuals in the last five
38 years (Curtis and Lehner, 2019). The SE has enabled the emergence of non-traditional business
39 models in various traditional industries (Vaughan and Daverio, 2016); such as Airbnb
40 (Accommodation), Uber (Transportation), VizEat (Food), Hopwork (Business Services) or
41 Kiva (Finance). Furthermore, the appearance of the SE has generated disruptive innovation in
42 those traditional sectors (Guttentag, 2015).

43 On a societal and economic level, the relevance of SE activities is undeniable, being a
44 phenomenon of great economic relevance and impact with unquestionable growth. Various
45 institutions (e.g., the European Commission, PriceWaterhouseCoopers, eMarketer) have
46 analyzed the increasing use, transactions, and revenues of the services provided by the SE.
47 According to eMarketer (2019), in 2018, 32% of U.S. Internet users participated in SE services,
48 and this figure is expected to grow to 41% in 2022. As an example, eMarketer (2020) establishes
49 that in 2019, Airbnb had 42.1 million adult users in the U.S. and it is estimated that by 2023, it
50 will reach 48.1 million. Moreover, in 2019, U.S. home-sharing had 57.7 million adult users,
51 and this is expected to reach 69.2 million by 2023. In a study to measure SE activity in Europe,
52 Vaughan and Daverio (2016) estimated that collaboration platforms generated revenues of
53 almost 4.5 billion dollars and facilitated 31 billion dollars of transactions within Europe in 2015.
54 Similarly, the European Commission (2017) states that in 2016 there were around 323 SE-
55 related platforms active in the European Union (+ Norway). Finally, across the world, according
56 to estimations by Vaughan and Hawksorth, (2014), the SE generated revenues of around 15
57 billion dollars in 2013, and it is expected to reach around 335 billion dollars in 2025. This study

58 also argues that the traditional rental sectors generated 16 times more revenue (about \$240
59 billion) than the SE sectors in 2013, but by 2025 it is estimated that both sectors will have
60 similar revenues, which would mean 40% growth for the traditional sectors and more than
61 2000% growth for the SE sectors.

62 On the academic level, various higher education institutions have begun to offer subjects as part
63 of their curriculums in one or more bachelor's and master's degrees (e.g., King's College
64 London, Copenhagen Business School) or complementary courses (e.g., Stanford University)
65 dedicated to the SE. On a theoretical level, the increased consideration from academics
66 regarding the SE has led to the appearance of special issues in scientific journals, such as
67 *Journal of Business Ethics*, *Entrepreneurship Theory and Practice*, *Journal of Business*
68 *Research*, *Journal of Management Studies*, or *Journal of Cleaner Production*. Besides,
69 publications in this field of study can be found in most of the FT Research rank journals.

70 All of this increasing relevance has meant that the literature on SE has spread very quickly,
71 which has led to a certain complexity and contradiction when addressing this field (Acquier et
72 al., 2017; Hossain, 2020). Moreover, as it has been more than 40 years since the first article on
73 the SE appeared (i.e., Felson and Spaeth, 1978), and since this field, it is still searching for its
74 own identity and definition, it is particularly necessary to study the intellectual and cognitive
75 structures of the SE. By doing that, it will be possible to analyze the ascending and descending
76 influence patterns of certain seminal works overtime, to identify focus areas of study, and to
77 discover new potential avenues of research. Although recent review papers (e.g., Ertz and
78 Leblanc-Proulx, 2018; Hossain, 2020) have been found in this field, to the extent of our
79 knowledge, we can verify that there are no studies that conducted an exhaustive, extensive, and
80 updated analysis from an empirical point of view on the health and intellectual and cognitive
81 structures of this field. To this end, this study applied a combined use of three bibliometric
82 techniques.

83 First, to study the health of the field, this research estimates the concentration/diversification of
84 the distribution of citations and the ascending and descending influence patterns of the most
85 relevant articles in various periods through citation analysis. Secondly, to analyze the
86 intellectual structure, the broad thematic areas of this field will be recognized through a co-
87 citation analysis, using the statistical techniques of cluster and multidimensional scale analysis.
88 Finally, to explore the cognitive structure, the identification of past researched topics and future
89 research trends would be revealed through a co-occurrence analysis.

90 Thus, this paper contributes to the SE literature by outlining the discipline's structure as we
91 know it today. By reviewing 941 articles published in WoS from 1978 to 2019 on SE literature
92 and by establishing the appropriate criteria, this study not only explores the underlying structure
93 of this field, but we also ensure the replicability of this study, thereby responding to a recurring
94 problem in the economics literature (Maniadis and Tufano, 2017). The findings show the latent
95 concentration in the distribution of citations between articles and how newer publications
96 (articles with an ascending pattern) are gradually replacing the older ones (articles with a
97 descending pattern). It also discloses the existence of four main areas of research (hospitality
98 and tourism, consumer behavior, business models, and sustainable impact) and reveals
99 emerging research trends that can guide the development of this field.

100 **2. Background to sharing economy research**

101 While there is no single appropriate or agreed definition for the SE (Hossain, 2020; Sánchez-
102 Pérez et al., 2020), it is described in the literature as a phenomenon for the promotion of more
103 sustainable consumption practices that allow access to ownership of underutilized assets to
104 enhance efficiency (Eckhardt et al., 2019). This lack of consensus on a definition probably
105 stems from the fact that this field has been undergoing a rapid proliferation of studies coming
106 from a variety of disciplines and about a diversity of industries (Laurenti et al., 2019), which
107 has also caused the SE to be labeled with different names, such as collaborative consumption

108 (Barnes and Mattsson, 2016), collaborative economy (Felson and Spaeth, 1978), peer to peer
109 exchange (Aloni, 2016), peer economy (Tussyadiah and Pesonen, 2016), access economy
110 (Acquier et al., 2017), peer to peer sharing (Cheng, 2016), or legal access (Morewedge et al.,
111 2020). Indeed, this growing interest in SE research from various points of view has meant that
112 its nature and scope has continued to expand, which in turn has generated some controversy,
113 confusion, and complexity surrounding its intellectual and cognitive structures (Acquier et al.,
114 2017; Kraus et al., 2020). For these reasons it is necessary for review studies (e.g., systematic
115 analyses, bibliometric analyses) to be carried out periodically to highlight progress and
116 limitations, to stimulate reflections on future research, and to guide progress in the field.

117 **3. Bibliometric analysis in the sharing economy**

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119 Bibliometrics allows the study of publication patterns within a research field by quantitatively
120 analyzing empirical bibliographic data (DeBellis, 2009). It allows scholars to understand,
121 organize, synthesize, and guide a research discipline (Vogel and Güttel, 2013). Cobo et al.,
122 (2011) argue that bibliometric analysis not only encompasses performance analysis based on
123 scientific impact and the citations received by the articles but also that it should be accompanied
124 by science mapping techniques to visualize the evolution of the intellectual and cognitive
125 structures of a field.

126 An extensive literature review allowed us to identify up to ten review papers published between
127 2016 and 2020 on the SE; six bibliometric articles, two systematic reviews, and two literature
128 reviews (see Table 1). Cheng (2016) presented the first review article on the SE, albeit focusing
129 his analysis mainly on hospitality and tourism, and limiting his temporal search from 2010 to
130 2015. Similarly, other review papers (e.g., Curtis and Lehner, 2019; Ertz and Leblanc-Proulx,
131 2018) focused their work from the perspective of sustainability, intending to indicate
132 collaborative practices that are consistent with sustainable development. Sutherland and Jarrahi
133 (2018) also restrict their literature review, in their case, to the synthetization of the diverse

134 perspectives of technological mediation in the SE. In short, these works, by focusing on specific
135 perspectives, do not address the entirety of this field of study.

136 Although Lima and Carlos-Filho (2019) and Filimonova et al. (2019) did study the field as a
137 whole, adopting a bibliometric perspective, they oriented their work to the description and
138 characterization of works and the main research agents (authors, countries, institutions), i.e.
139 they presented mainly descriptive studies. Laurenti et al. (2019) presented a broad
140 characterization of 453 articles published between 1978 and 2017 in the Scopus database;
141 however they focused on classifying the articles according to the areas of knowledge, the
142 economic sectors they represent, and the actors and types of exchange involved.

143 Another bibliometric work, presented by Marín-Anglada and Hernández-Lara (2019) focuses
144 exclusively on citation analysis, leaving aside other complementary analysis techniques such
145 as co-citation or co-word analysis. Hossain (2020) carried out a systematic review with a sample
146 of 219 articles, but limits his search criteria to three-word pairs, “sharing economy”,
147 “collaborative consumption” and “collaborative economy”. Finally, Kraus et al. (2020) in a
148 more ambitious approach apply citation, co-citation, and co-word analyses to objectively
149 explore patterns in the SE literature, but they restrict their search to “shar* economy” as the
150 only research term and to articles published since 2013.

151 Beyond these ten review works, and as far as our knowledge extends, we can verify that there
152 are no studies that conduct a study such as the one being pursued here, i.e. focused on
153 identifying the intellectual and cognitive structures of the SE field, through a robust bibliometric
154 study that applies complementary techniques such as citation, co-citation, and co-word analysis
155 and with a wider spectrum in terms of time period and scope.

Author/s (year)	Title	Journal	Focus	Database/s	Study period	Keywords	Sample	Review type	Bibliometric method/s
Cheng (2016)	Sharing economy: A review and agenda for future research	International Journal of Hospitality Management	General + Tourism and Hospitality	EBSCOHost, Science Direct, and Google Scholar	2010-2015	“sharing economy”, “collaborative economy/consumption”	66 articles	Bibliometric review	Co-citation and co-word analysis
Ertz, & Leblanc-Proulx (2018)	Sustainability in the collaborative economy: A bibliometric analysis reveals emerging interest	Journal of Cleaner Production	Sustainability	Scopus and Web of Science	2010-2017	“sharing economy”, “collaborative economy”, “collaborative consumption”	729 articles	Bibliometric review	Co-authorship and co-citation
Sutherland, & Jarrahi (2018)	The sharing economy and digital platforms: A review and research agenda	International Journal of Information Management	General + Digital Platforms	Web of Science	2008-2017	thirteen terms + hyphenated variations	435 articles	Literature review (qualitative)	----
Curtis, & Lehner (2019)	Defining the Sharing Economy for Sustainability	Sustainability	Definitions	Scopus and Web of Science	1978-May 2017	thirty-eight terms	151 articles	Literature review (qualitative)	----
Lima, & Carlos-Filho (2019)	Bibliometric analysis of scientific production on sharing economy	Revista de Gestão	General	Scopus and Google Scholar	1978-2016	“collaborative consumption”, “sharing economy”, “collaborative economy”	95 articles	Bibliometric review	Co-authorship, co-citation, bibliographic coupling, and co-word analysis
Marín-Anglada, & Hernandez-Lara (2019)	Research on sharing economy: why are some articles more cited than others?	Economic Research	General	Scopus	2012-2018	‘sharing economy’ and ‘collaborative consumption’	212 articles	Systematic literature review	----
Laurenti et al. (2019)	Characterizing the Sharing Economy State of the Research: A Systematic Map	Sustainability	General	Scopus and Web of Science	1978-2017	“collaborative economy”, “collaborative consumption”, “sharing economy”	942 articles	Bibliometric review	Co-words analysis
Filimonova et al. (2019)	Trends in the Sharing Economy: Bibliometric Analysis	Book chapter	General	Web of Science	2010-2018	“sharing economy”, “gig economy”, “collaborative economy”, “p2p economy”, “peer-to-peer economy”, “collaborative consumption”	1311 articles	Bibliometric review	Citation analysis
Hossain (2020)	Sharing economy: A comprehensive literature review	International Journal of Hospitality Management	General	Scopus and Web of Science	1978-April 2018	“sharing economy”, “collaborative consumption”, “collaborative economy”	219 articles	Systematic literature review	----
Kraus et al. (2020)	The sharing economy: a bibliometric analysis of the state-of-the-art	International Journal of Entrepreneurial Behavior & Research	General	Web of Science	2013-February 2020	“shar* economy”	326 articles	Bibliometric review	Citation analysis, co-citation analysis, and co-word analysis

157 **4. Method**

158 *4.1. Data collection*

159 The Web of Science (WoS) database was chosen for the bibliometric analysis since it is
160 considered to be the main and comprehensive database of academic papers and the one with the
161 longest history as well as the one that contains the most prestigious academic journals, and
162 since it is frequently used for bibliometric analyses due to its “friendliness” and compatibility
163 with various software (Acedo et al., 2006; Mongeon & Paul-Hus, 2016). Through a literature
164 review and based on the ten previous papers that carried out literature reviews on the SE, the
165 following parameters were used to search for papers: *sharing economy*, *collaborative*
166 *consumption*, *collaborative economy*, *peer to peer exchange*, *peer-to-peer exchange*, *P2P*
167 *exchange*, *peer economy*, *access economy*, *peer to peer sharing*, *peer-to-peer sharing*, and *P2P*
168 *sharing* within the main WoS collection, taking into account the Science Citation Index
169 Expanded (SCI-Expanded), Social Sciences Citation Index (SSCI) and Arts & Humanities
170 Citation Index (A&HCI).

171 The search was conducted in February 2020 and the study period selected was 1978 to 2019,
172 since the first article included in WoS that contains the search parameter dates from 1978. We
173 have decided not to limit our search to one or several specific discipline/s (WoS category/ies)
174 due to three reasons; these are (1) the nature of the field, (2) the maturity of the field, and (3)
175 the objective of the study. The SE is considered a multidisciplinary field since it is born from
176 the connection and coexistence of diverse scientific areas to try to explain a single but complex
177 phenomenon (Acquier et al., 2017; Laurenti et al., 2019; Sánchez-Pérez et al., 2020). Restricting
178 its analysis to only one or even several disciplines will only bring partial and biased results.
179 Additionally, even if the SE emerged academically in an investigation by Felson and Spaeth
180 (1978), its take-off began about 10 years ago, and therefore it is still considered to be an
181 immature field (Kraus et al., 2020; Sánchez-Pérez et al., 2020). Finally, our objective is oriented

182 to determining the scope and the cognitive and intellectual structures of the SE; without
183 including the total sample of SE articles in our study it would not be possible to meet the set
184 objective. Indeed, in the words of Kraus et al. (2020), it is necessary to carry out bibliometric
185 works in the SE field that cover the total population of articles and we respond to this call in
186 our research.

187 To ensure the quality of the papers analyzed, the search was limited to articles only, excluding
188 review papers (to avoid duplication of documents), conference proceedings and papers to
189 congresses, books, and book chapters, as suggested by previous articles (e.g., Cheng, 2016;
190 Coombes and Nicholson, 2013). The use of WoS as a database and the stipulation of parameters
191 for the inclusion and exclusion of articles ensure the reproducibility of this research (Maniadis
192 and Tufano, 2017). Furthermore, the authors analyzed the titles, abstracts, and keywords of all
193 the articles identified for relevancy to SE literature. Non-relevant articles were deleted from the
194 sample (i.e., articles whose central content is not the study of the SE). The final sample
195 consisted of 941 articles. Since this study uses citations from these articles for citation, co-
196 citation, and co-occurrence analysis, citations received up to 31 December 2019 were included.

197 *4.2. Analysis techniques and tools*

198 For this research, we focus on three complementary bibliometric methods; namely, citation, co-
199 citation, and co-word analysis (see Figure 1). In citation analysis, citations are used as a measure
200 of influence. It is assumed that if an article is widely cited it is because several authors have
201 considered it important for their research (Zupic and Čater, 2015). It seems likely that the most
202 cited documents have a greater influence on the progress of a scientific field than the less cited
203 (Ramos-Rodríguez and Ruíz-Navarro, 2004). Hence, citation analysis allows ascending and
204 descending influence patterns of works overtime to be revealed and thus dynamically illustrate
205 the transformations that have taken place within a scientific field (Köseoglu et al., 2015).
206 Therefore, we have carried out first a document citation analysis (Zupic and Čater, 2015) with

207 the citations extracted from WoS and the help of Microsoft Excel 2010. To analyze the
208 concentration/diversification in the distribution of citations within this field, an adapted version
209 of the Lorenz curve was plotted. For this purpose, all works in the sample (i.e., 941 articles)
210 and the citations received by these works have been used. Additionally, to analyze the changes
211 of influence that the main works in this field have undergone, this phenomenon has been
212 graphically represented following the proposal of Ramos-Rodríguez and Ruíz-Navarro (2004).
213 As suggested by previous works (e.g., Ramos-Rodríguez and Ruíz-Navarro, 2004; Shafique,
214 2013), the 50 most cited articles and the citations received by them in a certain period of time
215 (2014-2019) were used.

216 Secondly, co-citation analysis enables the study of a network of references cited together
217 (Small, 1980). The essential supposition is that co-citation groups disclose the core intellectual
218 structure of a scientific field (Chen et al., 2010). Ramos-Rodríguez and Ruíz-Navarro (2004)
219 postulate that this technique allows the identification of focus areas of study within a research
220 field since the references represent the development and invisible relationships of the research
221 field and point out its influences. As such, it enables the recognition of the structure and
222 theoretical foundations, by revealing the affinity and proximity between publications (White
223 and Griffith, 1981) since frequently cited documents exert an overall influence on a discipline
224 (Culnan, 1986). Thus, a document co-citation analysis was carried out. Data calculation,
225 refinement, and treatment of citations from WoS were carried out using the BibExcel program
226 (Persson et al., 2009). Then, to obtain an automatic classification of documents, a hierarchical
227 cluster analysis was executed using the Ward method, and then a non-hierarchical cluster
228 analysis (Griffiths et al., 1984). Furthermore, as a confirmatory method, a multidimensional
229 scale (MDS) analysis was carried out. SPSS software was used for both cluster and MDS
230 analyses. For the co-citation analysis, following suggestions from previous works (e.g., Ramos-
231 Rodríguez and Ruíz-Navarro, 2004) and taking into account the limitation of SPSS for MDS

232 analysis (it does not permit calculation of correlations matrices of greater dimensions than 100),
233 the 100 most cited articles of our sample were taken into account ($\text{Stress} < 0.025$).

234 Thirdly, co-word analysis allows the keywords used by authors to characterize their works to
235 be examined, to establish relationships and build a conceptual structure of the main themes
236 within a scientific field (Callon et al., 1983). The premise is that when keywords appear
237 frequently in various documents, it means that the concepts behind those words are closely
238 related (Zupic and Čater, 2015). The result is a semantic map that helps us to understand the
239 cognitive structure of a field (Börner et al., 2005). The analysis of a series of such maps
240 produced for different periods enables the changes in this conceptual space to be traced. In this
241 way, associations and interactions between past research topics and emerging research trends
242 can be identified (Callon et al., 1991). For the co-occurrence analysis, SciMAT software was
243 used, as it helps to create scientific maps in a longitudinal framework (Cobo et al., 2012).
244 SciMAT is a widely used tool that is both highly robust and efficient to carry out co-word
245 analysis (see a review in Moral-Munoz et al., 2019). The main advantage of SciMAT is that it
246 helps to identify which thematic areas have received the most attention from researchers within
247 a specific field through the generation of strategic diagrams (Cobo et al., 2012); that is, it allows
248 the evolution of research trends to be visualized over various periods by measuring the density
249 and centrality of each theme (Cobo et al., 2015). Therefore, SciMAT's strategic diagrams are
250 graphed in two dimensions with four quadrants. The themes that appear in the upper right
251 quadrant are called motor themes because they have a high density and strong centrality. This
252 means that these themes are well developed and relevant to the structure of a field. The lower
253 right quadrant covers the basic, general, and cross-cutting themes, i.e. they are important but
254 need to be further developed. The themes located in the lower-left quadrant represent themes
255 that have low centrality and low density and are therefore mainly emerging or disappearing

256 themes. The themes in the upper left quadrant are marginal to the field because they have well-
 257 developed internal links but irrelevant external links (Rodríguez-López et al., 2020).

258
 259 **Figure 1.** Design of the review strategy.

260 **5. Results**

261 *5.1. Performance analysis*

262 Figure 2 illustrates that the SE has been a topic of growing research interest over the last decade,
 263 as it shows a steady increase in the number of articles published since 2012. While only 3% of
 264 the total number of articles was published in the first thirty-five years (1978-2012) of research

265 on this topic, in the last three years (2017-2019) 84% were published. Figure 2 also illustrates
 266 that citations of articles have increased since 2012, although there is clearly a drop in citations
 267 of articles in 2018 and 2019, as these manuscripts have been exposed to fewer citations.

268 **Figure 2.** Evolution of published articles and citations from 1978 to 2019.
 269

270 From 1978 to 2019, 368 journals were identified as indexed in the WoS database that have
 271 published at least one article on the SE field. Table 2 shows the ten most productive journals
 272 during the study period. The journal with the most articles is *Sustainability* with 74 articles,
 273 followed by the *Journal of Cleaner Production* with 47 and the *International Journal of*
 274 *Hospitality Management* with 38 articles. However, out of these 10 most productive journals
 275 the one with the most citations is the *Journal of Business Research* with 771 citations, followed
 276 by the *Journal of Cleaner Production* and the *Journal of Tourism Management* with 532 and
 277 460 citations respectively. If we take into account the average number of citations per article
 278 (C/A), the *Journal of Business Research* is again at the top with 64.25 citations per article. It is
 279 worth noting that nine of the ten journals belong to the first quartile (in different categories) of
 280 the *Journal of Citation Report*; the only exception is *Sustainability*, which belongs to the second
 281 quartile. Another point to note is that of the ten journals, five are devoted to the hospitality and
 282 tourism industries, which reflects the importance of these in the development of the SE.

Journal	A	C	C/A	JCR quartile
Sustainability	74	173	2,34	Q2
Journal of Cleaner Production	47	532	11,32	Q1
International Journal of Hospitality Management	38	440	11,58	Q1
International Journal of Contemporary Hospitality Management	27	366	13,56	Q1
Technological Forecasting and Social Change	20	392	19,60	Q1
Current Issues in Tourism	14	75	5,36	Q1
Tourism Management	14	460	32,86	Q1
IEEE Access	13	15	1,15	Q1
Journal of Travel & Tourism Marketing	12	140	11,67	Q1
Journal of Business Research	12	771	64,25	Q1

Table 2. The 10 most productive journals in SE research from 1978 to 2019.
A: Total number of articles; C: Total number of citations; C/A: Average number of citations per article.

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5.2. Citation analysis

287 Knowing that the main objective of citation analysis is to estimate the influence of articles
288 through citation rates, it has been deemed appropriate to analyze the relative
289 concentration/diversification in the distribution of citations among SE articles. Logic dictates
290 that concentration will exist; however, it is necessary to discern how great it is. To this end, an
291 adaptation of the Lorenz curve has been used, which allows us to graphically observe the
292 relative distribution of a variable in a given domain (Fellman, 2011). In this case, and as can be
293 seen in Figure 3, the horizontal axis represents the percentage of citations while the vertical axis
294 represents the percentage of articles. As data for these axes, as of December 31, 2019, this field
295 of study had 941 articles published in WoS, which had received a total of 10,916 citations.
296 At first glance, a pronounced concentration can be seen in the distribution of citations; for
297 example, the 8 most cited articles on this subject have 2,289 citations. These 8 articles are Belk

298 (2014), Hamari et al. (2016), Martin (2016), Zervas et al. (2017), Ert et al. (2016), Cohen and
299 Kietzmann (2014), Möhlmann (2015) and Hamari (2013). An analysis of the percentage of
300 citations reveals that 40% of citations are concentrated in 29 articles, or 80% in 191 articles;
301 leaving only 20% of citations for more than 750 articles. Nevertheless, it is important to
302 emphasize that this field, being in an early stage of research, has many recent publications,
303 which have not been exposed to citations for a long time.

304
305 **Figure 3.** Lorenz curve on the relative distribution of citations over the article set.
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307 However, to see the real influence of an article over time, it is not enough to analyze its total
308 number of citations as it also is necessary to check if the presence of those citations is constant
309 over time. That is why, following previous works (e.g., Shafique, 2013), the present study
310 analyzes the change in influence that publications have undergone within a period of time.
311 Taking as a sample the 50 most cited works in this field of study between 2014-2019 (since
312 2014 is the year in which the number of citations increases), the changes in the percentages of
313 citation are analyzed to reveal the gains or losses of influence over the period under study and
314 thus obtain a dynamic image of the transformations that have taken place within the discipline.
315 Figure 4 shows the changes in the comparative citation percentages for the different sub-periods
316 considered. The darkest band shows the percentage gain or loss of influence, from the first sub-

317 period (2014-2015) to the second (2016-2017), and the lightest band shows the percentage
318 difference from the second sub-period (2016-2017) to the third (2018-2019).

319 All the papers analyzed in the study fit a limited number of patterns (White and McCain, 1998).

320 One of the most common, known as up-up pattern, is that papers increase their influence from
321 the first to the second sub-period and repeat the process from the second to the third. This, of
322 course, indicates an ascending influence pattern throughout the study period; examples of works
323 that exhibit this pattern are Hamari et al. (2016), Martin (2016), Cheng (2016), Tussyadiah and
324 Pesonen (2016), and Zervas et al. (2017).

325 Another discernible pattern, known as up-down pattern, is the one that shows works with an
326 ascending profile between the first and second sub-periods but descending towards the end of
327 the period. This may indicate that the works in question reached and exceeded their maximum
328 weight of influence during the period in question, and seems to suggest that those with the
329 ascending pattern, mentioned above, have not yet reached that point. Some works that follow
330 this pattern are Belk (2014), Hamari (2013), Heinrichs (2013), and Albinsson and Perera
331 (2012).

332 Theoretically, other possible patterns would be that of works which lose influence at the
333 beginning only to gain it later (down-up pattern), although there were no cases of this nor of
334 another possible pattern which would be of works whose influence decreases in both the second
335 and third sub-period (down-down pattern).

Figure 4. Changes in the influence of 50 most cited articles in SE research (2014–2019).

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5.3. Co-citation analysis: detection of sub-fields of research

340 The application of the inter-group linkage cluster method has allowed the identification of four
341 clusters of articles. A close examination of the articles included in each cluster has allowed us
342 to characterize them. The clusters identified are (C1) Hospitality and Tourism, (C2) Consumer
343 behavior, (C3) Business models, and (C4) Sustainable impact.

- 344 • Cluster 1 (Hospitality and Tourism), which is made up of 32 articles, and therefore is the
345 bigger cluster, mainly consists of articles with strong ties to hospitality and tourism. The
346 majority of articles are published in journals such as *International Journal of Hospitality*
347 *Management, Annals of Tourism Research, Tourism Management, and Current Issues*
348 *in Tourism*. This cluster, which encompasses studies that analyze the main platforms
349 used for consumer accommodation (e.g. Airbnb and Couchsurfing), examines society's
350 reputation and trust in these and analyze the impact of the SE in hospitality and tourism
351 industries. Papers such as those presented by Guttentag (2015), Dredge and Gyimóthy
352 (2015), and Cheng (2016) are the seminal ones within this cluster. These papers
353 highlight the rise of the “informal” tourism accommodation sector (Guttentag, 2015),
354 critically assess the implications of the SE for tourism industry systems (Dredge and
355 Gyimóthy, 2015) and identify areas of focus for SE research in hospitality and tourism
356 (Cheng, 2016).
- 357 • The second cluster (Consumer behavior), comprising 28 manuscripts, draws mainly on
358 marketing and applied psychology theories to explain what leads consumers to choose
359 the SE over traditional firms. It focuses mainly on consumer decision-making,
360 anthropological aspects, and access to SE through new platforms. The main
361 representative works of this cluster are the ones of Bardhi and Eckhardt (2012) and Belk
362 (2014). These authors primarily evaluate the growth of SE by arguing that “*the old*
363 *wisdom that we are what we own may need to be modified to consider forms of*
364 *ownership and uses that do not imply ownership*” (Belk, 2014). The manuscripts of this
365 cluster are mainly found in journals such as *Journal of Consumer Research, Journal of*
366 *Marketing and Journal of Consumer Behaviour*.
- 367 • The third cluster (Business models) finds its roots in the SE as a non-traditional business
368 model (e.g., Netflix and Zipcar). It addresses issues such as the relevance of the internet

369 in this type of business, the growth of car-sharing and ridesharing businesses, and the
370 competition of SE businesses versus traditional ones. Important works include
371 Möhlmann (2015) and Hamari et al. (2016), who empirically prove the importance of
372 information and communication technologies (ICT) for the SE and highlight certain
373 factors (usefulness, trust, cost savings, familiarity, service quality, and community
374 membership) as factors that differentiate this type of non-traditional business model
375 from traditional ones. This cluster encompasses 29 articles distributed mainly in
376 journals such as *Journal of Business Research*, *Harvard Business Review*, *Business*
377 *Horizons*, and *Research in Transportation Business & Management*.

378 • Finally, cluster 4, which has the least number of manuscripts (11 articles), focuses on
379 the sustainable impact of the SE. Journals such as *Geoforum*, *Ecological Economics*,
380 and *Journal of Cleaner Production* stand out in this cluster. This group of articles
381 addresses issues such as the development of SE theory (what it is, its paradoxes, and its
382 link to sustainability) and social, economic, and environmental impact. The papers
383 presented by Cohen and Muñoz (2016) and Böcker and Meelen (2017) stand out as
384 relevant. These primarily analyze how some exchange activities could generate more
385 sustainable consumption and production and the relative importance of economic,
386 social, and environmental motivations in the shared use of tools, transport,
387 accommodation, cars, and catering.

388 To give greater robustness an MDS analysis has also been carried out. The MDS is a procedure
389 by which maps are made from the correlation matrix of the elements analyzed to explore the
390 structure underlying the entire set of elements. The MDS analysis, therefore, provides a graphic
391 vision of the different clusters (Acedo et al., 2006). Employing the MDS analysis and through
392 the identification of the works of each cluster (from cluster analysis) in the MDS map, we were
393 able to graphically confirm the existence of the four main areas of focus research on SE

414 been classified into four categories. The size of the sphere is proportional to the number of
 415 publications associated with each research topic and includes in it the number of citations
 416 corresponding to each of them.

417

(a) Period 1978-2016

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419

420

(b) Period 2017-2019

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Figure 6. Strategic diagrams.

424 **First period:** During the period 1978-2016, research was mainly distributed across 12 main
425 topics. Of those, seven relevant themes (four motor topics and three basic and transversal
426 themes) could be identified due to their contribution to the growth of the field under study
427 (Figure 6(a)); these are *entrepreneurship*, *collaborative consumption*, *market*, *space*,
428 *technology*, *behavior*, and *systems*. Each theme is approached from several points of view,
429 reflecting the increasing diversity of perspectives and the complex nature of the SE. For
430 example, *collaborative consumption*, which is the motor theme with greater impact (4,382
431 citations and h-Index of 31, see Table 3), encompasses research on changes in consumer
432 behavior, the connection to sustainability, and the transition of the community towards a
433 collaborative system (cf. Barnes and Mattsson, 2016). Standing out within the *entrepreneurship*
434 topic are viewpoints such as the entrepreneurship-innovation connection in creating value for
435 SE, the rise of the circular economy, or the analysis of the industries where the creation of
436 collaborative new ventures are most prominent (e.g., accommodation and tourism) (cf. Cheng,
437 2016).

438 Meanwhile, *space* is detected as another motor topic, referring to works that study the
439 peculiarity of shared spaces, such as, co-working spaces, or P2P accommodation with
440 communal spaces (cf. Tussyadiah and Pesonen, 2016). Finally, the last motor topic is *market*,
441 studied mainly through the economic and social impact of SE activities on the market, such as
442 the impact of Airbnb or Couchsurfing in the hospitality industry and their subsequent impact
443 on hotel rates and consumer segmentation (cf. Dredge and Gyimóthy, 2015). As a basic topic,
444 *behavior* stands out by receiving a great number of citations (848) and this can be explained by
445 the huge interest of academics to understand not only the management perspective of the SE
446 but also the consumer perspective (cf. Belk, 2014). *Technology* is placed as a basic topic, mainly
447 analyzing the use of the internet and other technological supporting tools and features, while

448 *systems* is a basic theme highlighting the perspective of the P2P system for the SE (cf. Belk,
449 2014; Tussyadiah and Pesonen, 2016).

450 In addition, Figure 6(a) presents one emerging theme (*online*) and one declining topic (*trust*),
451 and three peripheral themes (*tourism*, *marketplaces*, and *Uber*). From those, it should be noted
452 that *online* and *trust* were mainly approached to study SE-related e-commerce and intentions
453 respectively (cf. Belk, 2014; Ert et al., 2016), and that *online* has received a greater number of
454 citations while attracting fewer documents than *trust*. Finally, *tourism* was an internally well-
455 developed, although peripheral, topic. It was researched from a great variety of points of view,
456 including tourism development, tourism marketing, tourist culture, and through the inherent
457 link between hospitality and tourism (cf. Cheng, 2016).

458 **Second period:** During the period 2017-2019, the research is characterized by thematic
459 diversification, and is distributed across twenty main topics. Accordingly, seven motor themes
460 and four basic topics were identified (Figure 6(b)). *Sharing economy* appears as the theme with
461 the greatest impact on the three criteria analyzed (see Table 3). Studies on these topics are
462 divided into various perspectives: customer satisfaction, innovation, sustainability, and trust.
463 This shows the complexity of the SE when studied from a wide variety of points of view
464 (Hossain, 2020). *Framework* is the topic with the second greatest impact on the three criteria.
465 It encompasses research related to business models, ecosystems, and innovation networks (cf.
466 Kumar et al., 2018). Two other relevant motor themes in this period are *determinants* and
467 *tourism*. Within the *determinants* theme, a great variety of attributes are studied that consumers
468 take into account when making decisions, such as hedonic price, real price, market, and hotels
469 vs. Peer-to-peer accommodation (cf. Wang and Nicolau, 2017). On the other hand, the *tourism*
470 topic, which has gained great relevance concerning the first period, highlights research areas
471 such as destinations, consumer perceptions, and second homes (cf. Hossain, 2020).

472

	Topic	Number of citations	Number of documents	h-Index
Period 1978-2016	Collaborative-consumption	4,382	62	31
	Entrepreneurship	905	22	14
	Online	900	9	7
	Systems	867	14	10
	Behavior	848	8	7
	Trust	566	15	11
	Uber	323	3	3
	Technology	314	7	6
	Space	270	7	7
	Market	268	8	6
	Tourism	175	5	4
	Marketplaces	122	5	4
	Period 2017-2019	Sharing-economy	4,302	636
Framework		1,366	246	21
Online		1,355	181	18
Tourism		1,139	141	19
Determinants		1,069	118	18
Sustainable-consumption		922	149	16
Car-sharing		907	150	15
Value-co-creation		828	115	16
Platforms		771	120	15
Big-data		684	98	15
Technology-acceptance-model		647	93	14
Governance		631	96	14
Word-of-mouth		564	75	15
Peer-to-peer-accommodation		426	104	13
Community		401	72	12
Performance		307	69	11
Demand		151	25	7
Geographies		106	18	8
Bicycle		73	6	4
Economic-impact		34	6	3
Perceived-risk	30	18	3	

Table 3. Performance of topics in the periods 1978–2016 and 2017–2019.

473
474
475 The other three motor themes in this period are *word-of-mouth*, *model of technology acceptance*
476 *and car-sharing*. Within *word-of-mouth* a number of interesting viewpoints can be found such
477 as perceived value and online consumer assessments, e-commerce usage, and brand value (cf.
478 Liang et al., 2018). Within the theme *technology acceptance model*, perspectives such as
479 consumer behavior and behavioral intent based on the theory of planned behavior are addressed
480 (cf. Wang et al., 2020). Finally, *car-sharing* highlights customer experiences such as
481 preferences and behavior for mobility and its impact (cf. Habibi et al., 2017). *Value-co-creation*,
482 *sustainable consumption*, *online*, and *platforms* appear as incipient topics requiring further
483 development. *Value-co-creation* research is focused on business models innovation, social
484 practices, and social actors (cf. Camilleri and Neuhofer, 2017), while the *sustainable*

485 *consumption* topic concentrates on access-based consumption, people's attitudes, and the
486 circular economy (cf. Böcker and Meelen, 2017). The *online* theme encompasses research on
487 consumer satisfaction, virtual communities, reputation, and reciprocity. And the *platforms* topic
488 analyzes the dual market strategies that exist in SE activities (cf. Sutherland and Jarrahi, 2018).
489 In addition, Figure 6(b) shows six dilemma themes and four peripheral themes. The emerging
490 or declining themes are *community*, *geographies*, *peer-to-peer accommodation*, *performance*,
491 *big data*, and *perceived risk*. SciMAT allows not only the identification of themes by periods
492 but also enables the observation of their evolution over time on a longitudinal map (see Figure
493 7). As can be seen, the thematic areas where the SE field is developing are entrepreneurship,
494 collaborative consumption, space, market, trust, Uber, marketplaces, tourism, technology,
495 behavior, systems, and online, while in the most contemporary period, new topics have
496 appeared such as sharing economy, car-sharing, word-of-mouth, framework, technology
497 acceptance model, performance, governance, sustainable consumption, value co-creation, big
498 data, peer-to-peer accommodation, among others. Solid lines represent a thematic nexus
499 between the linked themes, as they are part of the main element, while a dotted line means that
500 the themes share elements that are not the main element (Cobo et al., 2012).

501 In general, research on the SE presents low cohesion between the two study periods, since there
502 are only two thematic areas, tourism and online, that appear in both periods. It is also worth
503 noting the evolution and name change of the thematic area from collaborative consumption to
504 sharing economy, which confirms this term as an umbrella term, which encompasses
505 collaborative consumption. Also, it can be seen that several topics have gained relevance over
506 time. The tourism theme changed from being a peripheral theme in the first period to being a
507 motor theme in the second period, indicating that it has gained relevance in the last three years
508 within the SE. This further reinforces the fact that this industry is the most important in this
509 field.

Figure 7. Longitudinal evolution map.

512 The online theme is another that has gained importance since it has progressed from being an
513 emerging theme to being a basic and transversal theme within this field. The development of
514 this topic can be understood as the confirmation of the technological nature of the SE with the
515 emergence of digital tools and platforms (cf. Sutherland and Jarrahi, 2018; Perren and Kozinets,
516 2018). Likewise, sustainable consumption has appeared in the second period as the evolution
517 of consumer behavior, demonstrating the increasing importance of this phenomenon within the
518 SE literature. It is also worth noting the emergence of isolated themes that do not relate to any
519 topic in the first period but appear directly in the second, such as demand, bicycle, economic
520 impact, and perceived risk.

521

522 **6. Discussion and implications for academic research**

523 By assessing the importance of certain articles within this field with a citation analysis using an
524 adaptation of the Lorenz curve, it could be argued that there is a great concentration in the
525 distribution of citations within this field. Although this might indicate the existence of seminal
526 works for the development of SE research, since citations in this scientific field are very
527 concentrated in a small number of manuscripts, it could also show a skewed citation distribution
528 that could mean an over-citation of these few manuscripts (Bertoli-Barsotti and Lando, 2019).
529 However, by exploring the 50 most influential articles, it can be seen that, as is typical of
530 “normal science” (Latour, 1987), newer publications present an ascending pattern, and are
531 gradually replacing the older ones (descending pattern), which in turn reveals a healthy growth
532 of the field (Shafique, 2013).

533 From a macro-perspective, thanks to the extensive analysis of 40 years of publication, this paper
534 is not a review or ‘synthesis’ of the accumulated body of research, but an exploration into the
535 development of the theoretical foundations of the SE as a scientific domain. As the frontiers of
536 SE intersect with several disciplines -management, marketing, economy, law, sociology,

537 technology-, we can expect new insights, extending our knowledge of the SE concept. In
538 particular, since interdisciplinarity is an approach increasingly seen as key to addressing
539 complex problems (Breslin et al., 2020), further research should pay attention to the
540 interdisciplinary nature of the articles published about SE. We extend this view by disclosing
541 the core intellectual roots that serve as the foundation stones for SE research through a co-
542 citation analysis in which we identify four main areas of research: hospitality and tourism,
543 consumer behavior, business models, and sustainable impact.

544 Three of these, hospitality and tourism, business models, and consumer behavior could be
545 considered as highly developed compared to the sustainable impact cluster. This shows that the
546 study of this cluster has been limited and that it is still in an incipient stage (Laurenti et al.,
547 2019). A further close examination of each cluster reveals the current focus of SE research lies
548 in the importance of reputation, trust, and ICT for customers (Ert et al., 2016; Hamari et al.,
549 2016), the impact of SE businesses (e.g., Airbnb) on traditional businesses (e.g., hotels) (Zervas
550 et al., 2017), the influence sociological perspectives (Belk, 2014) on consumer decision-making
551 (Bardhi and Eckhardt, 2012), and on the use of digital platforms (Sutherland and Jarrahi, 2018),
552 the determinants of customer satisfaction (Möhlmann, 2015), and its link to sustainability
553 (Böcker and Meelen, 2017). In any case, it is certainly worthwhile endeavoring to gain a deeper
554 understanding of customers' sustainable consumption behavior in the SE, as this is an issue that
555 still requires further development (Cohen and Muñoz, 2016).

556 Although the results show that these main areas are the dominant ones in the SE literature, it
557 can be said that they are still unconnected streams of knowledge for which further work is
558 required to link them in order to contribute to the development of the intellectual structure of
559 this field.

560 This, in turn, will lead to the creation of an own identity for this field in general, and in
561 hospitality and tourism in particular. Moreover, it is essential to conduct studies that connect

562 the four research areas by taking as a basis the hospitality and tourism perspective, since this is
563 the main subfield within the SE literature. This could also have implications for the taxonomy
564 of hospitality products with SE as own category by itself.

565 Several specific research directions deserve more attention. From a micro-perspective, the
566 research focus should deepen the analysis of each of the four foundation stones.

567 Sub-field 1: Hospitality and tourism.

- 568 1. The applicability of conventional management principles in tourism and tourist
569 behavior need to be examined in the context of SE (Hossain, 2020; Wang and Nicolau,
570 2017). In this vein, topics such as peer-to-peer accommodation, car-sharing, consumer
571 demand, geographies, and tourism in general, have a high prominence in SE research.
- 572 2. Assessing the eWOM effects in the SE and their impact on the hospitality industry
573 (Liang et al., 2018).
- 574 3. Analyzing the dyadic relationships in online hospitality and tourism platform networks
575 by applying social network analysis (Chung, 2017).
- 576 4. Impact of the SE on the hospitality and tourism industry (Zervas et al., 2017).

577 Sub-field 2: Consumer behavior.

- 578 1. Given that issues related to consumer information, such as big-data, platforms, TAM,
579 eWOM, or perceived risk are gaining increased relevance as they have an undeniable
580 role as a growing data source for SE businesses (Xu et al., 2019), these are topics that
581 require further attention in SE research considering the privacy concerns they generate
582 among consumers (Bleier et al., 2020).
- 583 2. To delve into the theory of planned behavior in order to analyze how the risk perceived
584 by the consumer influences the business of the SE (Hong et al., 2019).

585

586

587 Sub-field 3: Business models

- 588 1. Disentangling the dominant logic of the sharing economy as a business model, through
589 its defining dimensions (Engelmann et al., 2020). Explicating the distinct skills,
590 processes, procedures, organizational structures, decision rules disciplines, and
591 performance that underlie the development of the SE (Kumar et al., 2018).
- 592 2. Examining the performance of governance mechanisms in the sharing economy
593 (Eckhardt et al., 2019).

594 Sub-field 4: Sustainable impact.

- 595 1. Specific research is needed to explore the micro foundations (e.g., shared knowledge,
596 value co-creation, sustainability), that have facilitated and enabled the development of
597 sustainable behavior in the SE, with a temporality perspective (Teece, 2007). In
598 particular, this exploration could be developed for SE to thrive in the New Normal
599 (Ahlstrom et al., 2020).
- 600 2. Analyze the reasons that have led to the development of the SE. Specifically, to
601 determine whether SE responds to an evolution in the mode of consumption, as
602 suggested by Bardhi and Eckhardt (2012), is it the result of a sustainable consumer
603 (Cohen and Muñoz, 2016), or is it just convenience (Böcker and Meelen, 2017).

604 Finally, as an extension of the bibliometric analysis, we firmly believe that applying other
605 techniques, such as bibliographic coupling, co-authorship or evolved knowledge domain
606 techniques could provide opportunities for a further understanding of the SE field by displaying
607 the conceptual and social roots of the field (cf. Vogel and Gütel, 2012). Furthermore, it would
608 be of interest to carry out a network analysis of authors to identify links and relationships (cf.
609 Zupic and Čater, 2015). Additionally, an important task to complement this study could be a
610 thematic analysis to uncover the ontology domain of the SE, i.e. inductively synthesizing and
611 categorizing it into major themes and sub-themes (cf. Jones et al., 2011).

612 **7. Conclusions**

613 This study makes a significant theoretical contribution to the SE research field by extending the
614 existing knowledge. The complementary use of citation, co-citation, and co-word analysis
615 enabled us to carry out an empirical and inductive study of the SE literature to examine the
616 health of this field, its intellectual and cognitive structures, patterns of influence, and to propose
617 future research directions.

618 From a theoretical perspective, this study presents a comprehensive review of a significant
619 number of WoS articles (941 in total, between 1978 and 2019) that complements existing
620 reviews on the SE, extending the period of analysis and providing new avenues for research. In
621 this regard, it should be noted that the most recent review studies in this field analyzed articles
622 published up to 2018, but in 2019 alone, 370 articles were published on this topic (representing
623 40% of total articles). It was therefore necessary to present a more up-to-date review analysis.

624 From an academic point of view, with this analysis, we help to bring clarity to the SE literature,
625 by plotting a thematic evolution map to understand the longitudinal progression of the research
626 field. We uncover the major areas of research and some prominent future research tendencies.

627 From a methodological perspective, this manuscript highlights the complementary use of
628 citations, co-citation, and co-word analysis to examine the underlying relationships of the
629 intellectual and cognitive structure of a field of study. From a practical point of view, diverse
630 interested agents (e.g., consumers, service providers, policymakers, SE new businesses,
631 traditional companies) will benefit from the holistic insight of the evolution and current status
632 of some aspects that are of their concern.

633 This study is not without some limitations. Firstly, this study examines only articles from
634 academic journals indexed in the WoS database. Second, the keywords selection may directly
635 condition the results, as the SE concept has evolved in recent years to the extent that different
636 terms are associated with it. Third, it should be noted that the sample of articles used for this

637 study includes articles published up to the end of 2019.

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